

GLOBALIZATION OF ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS AND PROBLEMS OF STATE SOVEREIGNTY

Kuldoshev Asliddin Tursunovich

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Samarkand State Architectural and Civil Engineering Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6669748>

Annotation

In this article globalization of ecological problems and issues of state's suzerainty and problem of prevention of natural atmosphere directly connected with matter of state's ecological suzerainty are investigated.

Key words: integration, universal, globalization, intensification, ecological suzerainty, natural resources, atmosphere, radioactive, hazardous chemical waste.

At the present time, the global ecological landscape of the world has been formed as a result of the anthropogenic, anthropotechnogenic, anthropolitic impact of mankind on nature and the evolution of ecological relations between peoples, nations, states. In this process, the influence of the "artificial environment" (engineering, technology, information communication and infrastructure systems and the process of urbanization) created by the human factor on the natural habitat of living organisms - the ecological balance of the historically formed biosphere - played a key role. In particular, the escalation of the negative consequences of the intensification of the processes of integration, universalization, globalization in the world is changing both the standards of socio-political lifestyle and the paradigms of science.

The process of globalization, which began in the second half of the twentieth century, on the one hand, introduced new qualitative changes in the organization of all spheres of human activity, in particular in international environmental political relations. But, on the other hand, this process has a negative impact on key components and areas of international life. That is, humanity's focus on changing the world — the expansion of its possibilities for creativity and destruction — is inevitably changing attitudes toward the issue of suzerainty. Indeed, in the current environment, where the atmosphere, water, soil pollution, depletion of non-renewable natural resources, without exception, adversely affect the interests of all people living on earth, the protection of the natural environment has become an international global strategic task.

Especially since the middle of the twentieth century, in a system of global environmental problems, planetary climate change; on the one hand, the "revision" of the criteria and principles for determining and assessing the

sovereignty of states in international relations in the context of global environmental problems and the development of the normative framework of international law of environmental sovereignty; on the other hand, in the context of growing egoistic, ethno-centric instincts that absolute the national-utilitarian, mercantile interests of some states, they require the creation of political mechanisms to prevent the use of transboundary natural resources and pollution of the atmosphere and water bodies.

In the use of transboundary natural resources of international environmental law, it is especially important to protect the ecological sovereignty of states other than the environmental aggression of states that actively influence climate change. Indeed, international environmental law is a set of internationally recognized principles and norms of international law aimed at managing and controlling the interaction of subjects of international law in the field of protection of the natural environment and rational use of its resources, and is the legal basis of environmental sovereignty.

In some countries, the excessive industrial and "intellectual pressure" of man on nature goes beyond national and regional boundaries, and in many cases, the inability of individual countries to deal with its consequences leads to the exclusion of "euphoria of sovereignty." Because the solution of global socio-political problems directly related to the fate of mankind, the prospects of civilization: (for example, international terrorism, environmental manifestations of extremism), the abuse of sovereignty of individual states - a way of large-scale cooperation based on international law indicates that this can be done.

In particular, if we look at the history of the use of the international community's ability to resolve interstate environmental conflicts in a particular region, L. Forrer, the Swiss representative at the Berne Congress on November 17-19, 1913, said: if it belongs to more than one country, the state cannot achieve the necessary results in its protection by its own efforts, or if the state's intervention harms the interests of its citizens and does not benefit nature protection, then all civilized states or their groups should be forced to adopt the style. "

The predominance of universal democratic and humanistic norms in the reality of the modern world requires "editing" the content and function of the classical concept of "state sovereignty". In particular, the escalation of global problems related to the use of transboundary natural resources and the elimination of air pollution raises the issue of considering this political and legal category on the basis of new criteria and, if necessary, limiting the sovereignty of some states in practice.

In accordance with these requirements, to coordinate the efforts of the world community in solving global problems, in particular, cross-border environmental problems, to combine the national economic and scientific-technical potential with the capabilities of the world community, to jointly solve environmental problems requires the aspiration to be consolidated at the level of constitutional law. Because cross-border environmental issues are a priority in the modern system of international relations, and their solutions are discussed at prestigious international conferences at the UN level.

Some scientific studies and official documents from international organizations suggest that the problem of protecting the planet's natural environment can be solved by forming a "single world government" or a "global environmental political system." In such views, there are elements of utopianism in the teachings. However, it must be acknowledged that the effectiveness of global policy in the field of environmental protection can be ensured only through the socio-political system of states, regardless of the ideological position of the subjects of international environmental policy, cooperation, ie international compromises and agreements between them.

In general, existing and planned international agreements are based on global cooperation in the field of environmental protection. In particular, the end of the arms race and disarmament: the development and use of nuclear weapons tests, neutron bombs; Proposals for a complete ban on chemical weapons and the destruction of its stockpiles reflect a spirit of concern not only for the protection of the planet's nature, but also a practical effort to maintain global security and the ecological sovereignty of states.

References:

1. Каримов, Б. Р., & Тураев, Б. О. (1985). Научное предвидение как высшая форма опережающего отражения действительности. /Предвидение как форма научного познания.
2. Эргашева, М. Х. (2022). Замонавий таълим синергетик тизим сифатида. Философия и жизнь международный журнал, (SI-1).
3. Жураев Ю.А. Вопросы экологического суверинитета Республики Узбекистан. // Фалсафа ва ҳуқуқ 2013, №2, -С.61.
4. Александров В., Моисеев Н. Ядерный конфликт – глазами климатологов и математиков. // Знание – сила. – 1992. - № 2.
5. Куддашев А. Экологическая социология: альтернативные прогнозы //Credo new. – 2013. – №. 3. – С. 11-11.
6. Khotambekovna, E. M. (2021). Systematic Analysis of Education. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 2(07), 85-96.

7. Quldoshev A. T. PROSPECTS FOR GLOBAL ENVIRONMENTAL SECURITY //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2021. – Т. 4. – С. 34-36.
8. Kuldoshev A. T. SYNERGISTIC APPROACH TO MANAGING GLOBAL ECOLOGICAL POLITICAL RELATIONS //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2019. – №. 11. – С. 560-564.
9. Кулдошев А. Т. ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ И ЭКОНОМИКА //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2015. – №. 12. – С. 44-47.
10. Tursunovich K. A. Synergistic approach: managing the global environment political relations //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 259-264.
11. Ризаев И. И., Муминова З. О. ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПОДГОТОВКА ЛИЧНОСТИ: ОЗДОРОВЛЕНИЕ И ДУХОВНОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ //СИСТЕМА МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА КАЧЕСТВА В ВУЗЕ: ЗДОРОВЬЕ, ОБРАЗОВАННОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТЬ. – 2021. – С. 264-268.
12. Сафаров А. И., Ризаев И. И. Этапы самоорганизации социальной системы //В поисках социальной истины. – 2021. – С. 237-242.
13. Сафаров А. И., Хаккулов Н. К. Свойственные качества совершенному человеку в суфизме //Современная наука как социально-политический фактор развития государства. – 2019. – С. 48-50.
14. Ҳаққулов Н. Қ. Сиддиқий-Ажзий маърифатпарварлик қарашларида миллий толерантлик масаласи //НамДУ илмий ахборотномаси-Научный вестник НамГУ. – 2020. – №. 10. – С. 296.